

PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS OF ENSURING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION IN GENERAL EDUCATION SCHOOLS

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ANNOTATION

In this article, the problems encountered in the educational process, the ways to positively solve them, and the issues of improving the quality of education are thoroughly studied. The research conducted by several professors and teachers, the shortcomings encountered during their pedagogical activities, and the experiences of foreign countries with developed educational processes were analyzed.

Key words: pedagogy, quality of education, social attitude, spiritual education, world experience, qualified specialist.

INTRODUCTION

The role and responsibility of public education is the main pillar in the development of the state and in ensuring the stability of political priorities. Knowledge is the main tool and resource for entering the ranks of developed countries in political, socio-economic, spiritual or other fields. While knowledge remains mostly in schools and educational institutions, it is shaped and strengthened in the family as well. The school creates the ground for training a highly qualified specialist working in a certain field. The ability of the state of general education schools to meet the requirements of the times in the education of the educated young generation, and the issues of positively solving the problems of ensuring the quality of education in schools appear as an urgent issue of today.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Among the local researchers, C. A. Toshtemirova [14], Khojamkulov UN [16], the possibilities of a cluster approach in ensuring the quality of education and training qualified personnel; Sh.Q. Mardonov[13] training and professional development of modern pedagogic personnel, M.M. Vakhobov [10] conducted research on the issue of modeling the work of improving the quality of education.

From CIS scientists V.A. Slastenin, M.V. Klarin, YE. I. A.I. Subetto [12], Varchenko [11] and other scientists conducted scientific research on the issues of ensuring the quality of education.

Generalization, analysis and synthesis methods were used in the research process.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

If we analyze the statistical situation, the number of general education schools in our republic is more than 10,000, and on average, more than 600 students study in each school. The number of students in our republic is more than 6,000,000. It is noteworthy that in my country there are opportunities for representatives of different nationalities to study in their mother tongue. In particular, there are more than 600 general education schools that teach in Turkmen, Kyrgyz, Tajik, Kazakh, Karakalpak and Russian languages. In order to improve the quality of education, in accordance with the programs developed jointly with private, creative, specialized schools and foreign educational institutions, Presidential schools were co-organized, where lessons are conducted mainly in English. One of the reforms being carried out in education is that outdated and ineffective legislation has been revised, amended, and additional laws and ordinances have been promulgated. In particular, September 23, 2020, Law No. 637 of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" (new edition); October 8, 2019, Decree No. 5847 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "On Approval of the Concept of Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", October 29, 2020, of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "Science - Decree No. 6097, October 29, 2019, on approving the concept of science development until 2030, Law No. 576 of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Science and Scientific Activities", July 24, 2020 , Law No. 630 of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Innovative Activities", December 31, 2019, "On Approval of the Concept of Continuous Spiritual Education and Measures for its Implementation" of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 1059 20 legal documents were revised and adopted in the field of school education development. In addition, in order to study the educational process of foreign countries and to apply effective priority directions in the field of pedagogy, the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan, on October 25, 2022, at the meeting of video selectors, told the officials to select 48 schools in Kashkadarya within a month, and from the next academic year they set the task of introducing the Finnish education system.

Despite the ongoing reforms, decisions and decrees issued for the development of the education sector, and their practical implementation, there are several problems of ensuring the quality of education in the education

sector, especially in general education schools. *We classified the problems that are an obstacle to ensuring the quality of education as follows:*

1. *The first problem is the problem of increasing the authority of our pedagogues.* Such as the lack of strong cooperation between the school and parents, parents' lack of trust in teachers, and the fact that they do not allow measures to be taken against their children. Today, despite the fact that several effective educational reforms are being implemented to increase the authority of teachers, there are many problems. Video recording of the teacher's lesson process by students, distribution to social networks, writing comments on this video has a negative effect on the teacher's psychology. You can say that it is not a problem if the teacher gives the lesson at a high level. The problem is that the teacher does not want to cause discussions on his Internet network, because there is a possibility of negative comments. In our opinion, the teacher should be punished not by the parents, but by the head of the institution. As a result of parents pampering their children more than the norm, trying to protect them, it has a negative effect on the educational process and the quality of education.

2. *The second problem is insufficient material and technical support.* In some foreign countries, the monthly salary of teachers is much higher than that of other professions. For example, in Japan, the monthly salary of a teacher is equal to the monthly salary of ministers. The average salary is up to \$4,000. In our country, an average teacher with a higher education is provided with a monthly salary of about 3,000,000 (\$250). That is, 15-16 times less. When calculating the correct monthly salary, it is necessary to analyze the state's development, annual budget, import, export potential and several other economic scales. In our area, the monthly salary of Japan is not necessary, but it should be sufficient to meet the needs of the teacher, to solve problems in his family and life. In addition, the teacher has obstacles based on unwritten laws. For example, there are still problems related to the repair of classrooms, the preparation of teaching aids at personal expense, and several other problems. There is a need to build about 300 new schools in our region. The number of teachers is also insufficient, especially in Russian language, mathematics, English language, informatics and information technologies, there are more vacancies than in other subjects. Vacancies in schools are not filled on time due to low monthly salary. If one problem is not solved in time, other problems will follow.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

It is possible to compare the current state of school education with the "frog syndrome". If we put a frog in water and slowly boil the water, the frog will

not try to get out of the water and will die. If you put a frog in boiling water, the frog will try to survive by jumping out of the water.

The same process can be compared to education, gradually one gets used to ignorance, suddenly negative opinions are expressed about the required knowledge, objections increase. Today, in order to ensure the quality of personnel, it is necessary to revise the process of admission of students to higher education and the procedure of attestation of teachers. Because low-quality personnel raise a low-quality generation. Problems in education hinder the sustainable development of the country. It is in accordance with the goal that the problems of school education should be solved systematically and purposefully.

Based on the analysis of the above problems, the following recommendations were developed:

1. Analysis of the effective education system of countries with advanced education system and implementation in the education sector of our republic.
2. Development of legal documents that ensure the teacher's inviolability.
3. Introduction of administrative responsibility for low-quality education.
4. Regulation of social relations between teachers, students and parents according to the requirements of the law, changes and additions to the articles of the code of administrative responsibility.
5. To increase the responsibility of parents in the upbringing of children, to hold parents responsible for negative attendance at school through the law.
6. To study and determine the legal bases of deficiencies not specified in education and legislation.
7. Strengthening the material and technical support of the school.
8. Adaptation of complex school textbooks to modern requirements based on the principle of systematicity, etc.

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